

Fig. S4 fruiting

Fig. S4. Morphometric PCA plot of informative fruiting traits ($n = 8$) in a paired analysis of 262 plants of *C. howellii* (purple triangles), putative *C. howellii* (downward lavender triangles) and *C. leichtlinii* (green diamonds). Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table 1, Fig. 2 map.